

Speculation on Particle - Wave Duality

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Special relativity, and not only Newtonian mechanics, is based on the idea of sharp x and t values. For example, a 4-vector (x, ct) transforms under a Lorentz matrix and x and t are assumed to be known exactly. Furthermore, for a constant velocity passing through $x=0, t=0$, one has $v=x/t$, suggesting that v is also completely sharp (no error bars).

In a previous note (1), however, we suggested that quantum time and spatial resolutions \hbar/E and \hbar/p arise from the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et+px$, i.e. $dA=0 = -E dt + pdx$. This notion of x and t resolutions seems to completely contradict the sharpness of (x,ct) and v (for a free particle constant) which are used to create special relativity in the first place. For instance, one may derive the 2x2 Lorentz matrix for $x=0, t \rightarrow x', t'$ by requiring $x'/t'=v$.

In this note, we try to investigate this contradiction. We base our arguments on the notion that x' and t' must be measured and this requires some kind of interaction. Even in Newtonian mechanics, the formal definition of $v=dx/dt$, where dx and dt are measured and cannot be zero. Thus, we suggest that dx and dt in $dA=0$ are linked with measurement which necessarily involves interaction. In the photon case, $A=0 = -Et+px$, where $x/t=E/p = c$ as well as $dx = \hbar/p$ and $dt=\hbar/E$ linked with $dA=0$. In other words, a measurement is associated with \hbar/E and \hbar/p even if one has the notion of sharp x and t value. The notion of $dA=0$ also carries over to a particle with rest mass, m_0 , leading to the special relativity imposed $dx=\hbar/p$ and $dt=\hbar/E$ resolutions which must be considered if an interaction occurs with the particle. This is the "wave" view. If no interaction occurs, one may consider sharp x, t values linked to a high resolution external ruler and clock. This, we argue, is the particle view.

Sharpness of x,t in Newtonian Mechanics and Special Relativity

Both Newtonian mechanics and special relativity make use of sharp x and t values. In Newtonian mechanics, one has $x(t)$, while in special relativity one defines a 4-vector (x,ct) with no error bars for x and t . Furthermore, for a particle with constant velocity, v , passing through $x=0, t=0$, one has $x=vt$.

In principle, however, one has to measure x and t . Formally:

$v=dx/dt$ ((1)) This suggests two measurements of x and two measurements of t .

As a result, a sharp velocity $v=x/t$, when considered in terms of measurement, really involves intervals dx and dt . These in turn are linked with interactions (measurements), so from the point of view of measurements/interactions, one does not really have sharp x and t values, unless these dx and dt values may be made negligibly small..Special relativity, however, seems to block this from happening.

The Case of the Photon

The photon is known to satisfy: $c = x/t = E/p$ ((2))

((2)) is consistent with a wave equation if $E = \hbar \omega$ and $p = \hbar k$.
One may also note that ((2)) is equivalent to:

$$A = px - Et = 0 \quad ((3))$$

Here A is a Lorentz invariant. In ((3)), x and t are completely sharp values, suggesting that $c = x/t$ is also sharp.

If one writes: $dA = 0 = p dx - E dt$ ((4)), considering p and E to be completely sharp, then a solution is:

$$dx = \hbar/p \quad \text{and} \quad dt = \hbar/E \quad ((4))$$

In other words, the sharp x, t scenario is now linked with x and t resolutions ((4)) which are manifested in 2-slit interference/diffraction experiments.

One may ask how ((4)) really arises. If one has a photon with c, x and t , such that $A=0$, why should one consider $dA=0$. The point seems to be that for a photon trajectory, $A=0$ for $x=0, t=0$ and other x, t trajectory points, but also for shifts of these, i.e.

$$x = x_0 + n \cdot \hbar/p \quad \text{and} \quad t = t_0 + n \cdot \hbar/E \quad ((5)) \quad \text{where } n \text{ is an integer.}$$

The points ((5)) are not on the photon trajectory, but still satisfy $A=0$. If the Lorentz invariant A is taken to represent points allowed by the photon according to special relativity, then ((5)) seems to lead to the notion of x and t resolutions, even though x_0 and t_0 are completely sharp. In other words, a theory (special relativity) which begins with sharp x, t values (infinite resolutions), leads to Lorentz invariants ($-Et + px = A$) which lead to $dA=0$ x and t resolutions yielding the same A values. Dx and dt are assumed to be associated with some kind of measurement. To bypass these arguments, it seems that one must argue that $dA=0$ leading to $x = x_0 + n \cdot \hbar/p$ and $t = t_0 + n \cdot \hbar/E$ ($n = \text{integer}$) is not important, which suggests that the notion of the Lorentz invariant A is not important. This view, however, does not respect special relativity.

One may note that these resolutions are directly linked to E and p which are created due to a physical interaction. (This is more clearly seen with a particle with rest mass, m_0 , but also applies to a photon. If a photon is emitted from an excited atom that is moving, an interaction was required to move the atom, including its electromagnetic fields.)

One may note that: ((3)) yields $c = x/t$ while ((4)) yields: $c = dx/dt$ ((6))

The expression $c = dx/dt$ is linked directly with measurement, while $c = x/t$ is not because it assumes no error bars for x and t . In other words, it assumes infinite resolution or extremely tiny (approaching 0) error bars. This is incompatible with $c = dx/dt$ as seen from ((4)). In other words, special relativity seems to impose for the photon very specific dx and dt error bars.

How then can one interpret ((6))? In principle, one may have a ruler in space and a clock in time which has a much better resolution than \hbar/E and \hbar/p . In such a case, the notion of almost sharp x_0 and t_0 seems to exist. Why should one be concerned with \hbar/E and \hbar/p ?

It seems that the reason may be linked to the notion of the measurement which involves an interaction with the photon. This photon has E and p and carries an internal x, t resolution $\hbar/p, \hbar/E$ which one cannot bypass. In other words, this internal resolution will show up in experiments (involving interactions) such as 2-slit interference-diffraction.

Thus, $x/t=c$ describes external motion through a space which has a very sharp resolution ruler and clock, but as soon as the particle/photon interacts, this external resolution is no longer applicable to the internal resolution of the photon and ((5)) becomes important. This, we argue, leads to the notion of particle-wave duality.

It is not the case that $x/t=c$ is not important. A photon moves through space from x_1 to x_2 and t_1 to t_2 and these are relevant values, even if they are almost sharp. The point is that if an interaction occurs at any x, t , then one must consider the internal resolution of the photon $\hbar/E, \hbar/p$. In fact, if one is only interested in the interaction, one may not really need to worry about a sharp x or t , but only focus on \hbar/p and \hbar/E as in the case of 2-slit interference. One is not really interested in the time the photon interacts with the slits or the exact x location of the slits as long as they are separated by about a wavelength.

Extension to a Particle with Rest Mass

The photon arguments above are linked to the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et+px$ which also holds for a particle with rest mass, m_0 . Thus, one may also write:

$$dA=0 = -Edt + pdx \quad ((7)) \quad \text{and obtain} \quad x=x_0+n*\hbar/p \quad \text{and} \quad t=t_0+n*\hbar/E$$

For a particle with rest mass, the trajectory is no longer along $A=0$, but the same measurement resolutions exist.

In other words, a A value for x, t maps it to a Lorentz invariant, but this same Lorentz invariant value applies to other x, t points given in ((7)). This leads to the notion of $x-t$ resolutions based on special relativity which should be applicable to measurements involving the particle with rest mass.

A particle with rest mass, m_0 , may move through space according to $x=vt$, where x and t are sharp as is v . These sharp values may be linked with a high resolution ruler and clock in space. This is fine as long as one does not consider an interaction with the particle. If one does, one must take into account the internal resolutions, dictated by special relativity, \hbar/p and \hbar/E which lead to 2-slit interference-diffraction for a particle with rest mass as well. The “wave” nature (probability wave) is linked with a measurement on the particle which cannot ignore the internal $x-t$ resolutions of the particle, even though these may be much rougher than a very high external resolution clock and ruler.

As a result, the “particle” view is one which uses an external ruler and clock of very high resolution, while the “wave” view is associated with interactions with the particle which must consider the special relativistic imposed internal resolutions of \hbar/E and \hbar/p .

Situations in Which One Only Considers the Wave Point of View

In the above, we suggest two scenarios for a particle-wave, arguing that the wave view is linked with interactions. It is possible to have a problem in which only the wave or interaction viewpoint is key as in the case of a single particle quantum bound state. Interactions occur with a potential, but these must consider the \hbar/p resolution in space. Given that one does not know when and where these interaction hits occur, it seems that one does not need to use a particle viewpoint, i.e. $x=vt$, in between interactions. One may consider only average energy to be conserved at each x . In such a case, however, each x point has infinite resolution, so one is considering a particle viewpoint linked with the average energy, even though the actual particle is associated with \hbar/p resolutions.

To see this concretely, consider $\exp(ipx)$ as representing the wave probability scenario of a particle (free particle wavefunction based on \hbar/p resolution). In a scenario in which one only considers interactions with the particle, which is what happens in a $V(x)$, one may write:

$$W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad ((8))$$

((8)) represents an OR probability situation, but only considers the probability of the particle, not $x=vt$ at any x,t . To find $a(p)$ values, however, one must impose the condition of a constant E at any x . Thus, x has infinite resolution and is linked with a particle view associated with the average kinetic energy:

$$KE \text{ ave}(x) = -1/2m \ dW/dx / W = \{\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)pp/2m \exp(ipx)\}/W(x) \quad ((9)).$$

$$KE_{\text{ave}}(x) = .5 m_0 \ v_{\text{rms}}(x)v_{\text{rms}}(x) \quad ((10))$$

Thus, $v_{\text{rms}}(x)$ is linked with a particle view, but the interactions $\exp(ipx)$ only use the wave view, i.e. the x resolutions imposed by special relativity, i.e. one which respects Lorentz invariance.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that special relativity assumes infinite resolution for x and t because it uses the 4-vector (x,ct) . In fact, one may derive the Lorentz 2×2 matrix using $x=0, t \rightarrow x', t'$ such that $v=x'/t'$ for a particle with rest mass, m_0 . Experimentally, the notion of x and t being very sharp might be associated with a very high resolution ruler and clock in space, even if an interaction with the particle does not occur. This, we argue, is the particle view, linked to external measuring devices.

If, on the other hand, an interaction with the particle occurs, one finds that it is not the external ruler and clock which define this interaction. Instead, special relativity: $dA = -Edt + p \ dx$ (for both a photon and particle with rest mass) leads to internal resolutions of $dt=\hbar/E$ and $dx=\hbar/p$. These cannot be ignored in an interaction and give rise to physical results for 2-slit interference which are not described by the particle view which considers infinite $x-t$ resolution.

Thus, special relativity contains the dual nature by having infinite resolution for (x, ct) , but at the same yielding \hbar/E and \hbar/p from $dA=0= -Edt+pd x$, where $A= -Et+px$ is a Lorentz invariant. The resolution dx , and dt only come into play when there is an interaction because otherwise one may imagine the particle moving through x and t which are sharply defined by the external ruler and clock.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Entropy for a Particle in a Box, Special Relativity and Constraints (preprint, zenodo, 2024)